

Solutions for Building Urban Government towards Lean, Efficient, and Effective

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Abstract

This article analyzes the need for innovation in urban governance models in the context of rapid urbanization and the increasing demand for services for citizens. The focus is on building a streamlined, effective, and efficient urban government through organizational restructuring, rational decentralization and delegation of power, increased accountability of leaders, and accelerated digital transformation. In addition, improving the quality of the workforce, enhancing public service delivery processes, and promoting the supervisory role of citizens are considered key solutions. The article affirms that a streamlined and modern urban government model not only contributes to improving the efficiency of state management but also creates momentum for socio-economic development and improves the quality of life for urban residents.

Keywords: *urban governance; streamlined, effective, and efficient; Vietnam.*

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Introduction

In the context of rapid urbanization and increasingly demanding state management, building a streamlined, effective, and efficient urban governance model has become an essential need. Modern cities are not only economic, cultural, and social centers but also densely populated areas, giving rise to many complex issues that require a flexible, professional, and modern administrative apparatus. However, the organizational and operational models of urban governments in many places remain cumbersome, with overlapping functions, and the effectiveness of serving citizens and businesses does not match their potential. In this context, the need to innovate the administrative apparatus, improve the quality of the workforce, promote the application of digital technology, and perfect the mechanism for smart urban governance has become urgent. Building a streamlined, effective, and efficient urban government not only aims to meet the needs of modern governance but also makes a significant contribution to sustainable development, improving the quality of life for citizens and increasing the competitiveness of the city.

Research Content

Overview of Relevant Research

Entering the 21st century, the global trend of urbanization has intensified, profoundly impacting the economy, society, and people's lives. Two main trends in urban development have been identified: *First, Economic growth and structural transformation*: Many countries are witnessing a shift of labor from agriculture to industry and services, leading to a rapid increase in urban population. In particular, Asia has become a focal point for investment and growth, with a growing number of large cities with over 10 million inhabitants. According to the World Bank, this number increased from 20 cities in 2005 to 36 by the end

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of 2016. *Secondly, the development of satellite city systems* : To reduce pressure on central cities, many countries have built satellite cities to exploit the potential of smaller cities while improving transportation connections between them. Governments have implemented policies to invest in infrastructure and distribute industries to reduce concentration in large cities.

With two prevalent urban development trends worldwide, numerous studies have been conducted on this issue, specifically: Regarding urban development in the US, the study " *The Nature of Metropolitan Governance in Urban America: A Study of Cooperation, Conflict, and Avoidance in the Kansas City Region*" has been published. (Translation: *The Nature of Urban Management in the United States: A Study of Cooperation, Conflict, and Avoidance in the Kansas City Area*), by Curtis H. Wood (2005), presented at the Community Building Cooperation Conference held at Wayne State University, Detroit, MI, from October 31 to November 1, 2005, demonstrated that the dominant urban management model in the Kansas City area across 46 cities and 28 public services is one of intergovernmental cooperation. The study showed that intergovernmental service agreements are increasing when a city transfers services to another public organization or a city specializes in regional services (Curtis H. Wood, 2005).

The authors Brenner, Neil, and Christian Schmid, in their study " *Planetary urbanization*" also points out that the challenges and opportunities of urbanization trends that countries must overcome include the significant expansion in space and population of large megacity areas. This has significantly affected the rapid development of cities and the governance process in cities around the world today (Brenner, Neil, and Christian Schmid, 2012).

Research " *Ideology and practice in municipal government reform: A case study of Austin*" (Translation: *Ideology and practice in city government reform: A case study of Austin*), author Frank Staniszewski presented the urban government model through the case of Austin. According to the author, for the urban government model to work effectively, it is necessary to best utilize resources from the population to solve the problem of providing public services. Widespread participation and ensuring autonomy for citizens and businesses in solving community problems on the basis of strong decentralization is an important factor to ensure effective government operation (Frank Staniszewski, 2007).

In Bernd Stöver's work " *Arthur Schopenhauer*," Berlin is analyzed as a unique and unified community following the reunification of Germany on October 3, 1990. After becoming the capital of the entire Federal Republic of Germany, Berlin not only plays a political role but also has a unique administrative structure: a "3-in-1 city," meaning it is a city, a state, and a territorial administrative unit. Berlin is divided into 12 Bezirke (districts), each equipped with its own administrative apparatus and public service offices. The Berlin Constitution stipulates that the State Parliament consists of members from various parties, while the state government is run by the Mayor and 8 members. The city tends to reduce the number of administrative units, focusing on proximity to the people and local self-governance (Peter B. Lewis, 2012).

Authors Mike Barlow and Cornelia Lévy-Bencheton in their book " *Smart cities, smart future*" argued that within the next 20 years, 70% of the world's population will live in urban areas. Exponential changes will overwhelm people. The design and operation of smarter cities is not just a trend – it is the inevitable model of the future and the culture that we can all work together to build. An entire ecosystem is needed – including government, citizens, businesses and academia – to ensure that we do it right and everyone takes responsibility, without exception (Mike Barlow and Cornelia Lévy-Bencheton, 2020).

The book " *Urban Governance in Transition*" by author Hongshan Yang studies urban governance in China in the modern context. The author has identified four basic governance methods, including: All-powerful government method, Autonomous governance method, Integrated governance method, and Cooperative governance method. In addition to describing these methods, the book also analyzes hot topics in urban management today, such as: Development of urban management institutions, Relationship between cities and districts, Cross-border governance, Inter-sectoral coordination, Street management, and Community service provision (Hongshan Yang, 2021).

In Vietnam, the process of urban transformation and development is organized, analyzed, and evaluated

according to historical stages, analyzing arguments to demonstrate that each urban development process should prioritize economic growth based on the application of growth pole theory. In the context of globalization and international integration, Vietnam, like other Asian countries, is witnessing significant changes in both rural and urban areas. Studying urban transformation in relation to rural areas, local areas, the nation, and the global context, as well as in the past and present, offers significant scientific and practical implications.

The book "Globalization and Urban Transformation in Contemporary Vietnam" by the group of authors Pham Quang Minh, Nguyen Van Suu, Le Ang and Gay Hawkins (Editors) clarified urban developments through different spatial and temporal contexts. The group of authors discussed many aspects of urban transformation, including population and migration, livelihoods, religion, beliefs, cultural practices and social and environmental issues. The studies in the book require a collaborative, integrated and interdisciplinary approach to better understand these transformations in the process of modernization and globalization (Pham Quang Minh, Nguyen Van Suu, Le Ang and Gay Hawkins, 2016).

Nguyen Viet Dinh in the article "Migration from rural to urban areas - Some policy recommendations" published in the Journal of State Management (online), December 22, 2020 [**Error! Reference source not found.**], analyzed the relationship between rural and urban areas through spontaneous migration from rural areas to large cities in Vietnam. At the same time, the article pointed out the major challenges that need to be solved for socio-economic development in the process of migration from rural to urban areas. Therefore, the State and local authorities need to pay attention from a policy perspective to the issue of migration from rural to urban areas (Nguyen Viet Dinh, 2020).

In their article " *Urban Development in Vietnam Towards the Goals of 2030, Vision to 2045*," published in the Communist Magazine (online) on May 5, 2021, Vu Trong Lam and Nguyen Thi Diem Hang assessed the achievements in urban development in Vietnam. The authors also highlighted the difficulties and limitations in urban development in Vietnam over the past period, such as: *Firstly*, the rapid pace of urbanization has resulted in low quality. *Secondly*, many cities have high population growth rates, putting significant pressure on infrastructure and affecting the quality of public services. *Fourthly*, cities face a number of global issues such as: international integration, urban competition, environmental pollution, climate change, ... especially complex issues of urbanization and urban development such as migration, wealth inequality, housing, labor, employment, suburban development, urban-rural linkage (Vu Trong Lam - Nguyen Thi Diem Hang, 2021),

In the book "Organization of State Power at the Local Level" by Vu Thu, it was stated that in a country, state power is organized nationwide, with the establishment of central and local governments in administrative-territorial units. In modern states, the organization of state power at the local level follows the direction of rational decentralization and delegation, both demonstrating universality and reflecting national specificity; at the same time, power is exercised with characteristics of democracy, transparency, responsibility, rule of law, and efficiency (Vu Thu, 2019).

Author Le Cam Ha in the study "*Urban Government in Vietnam - From the perspective of practical management*" stated that: Building urban government is an important and difficult content in the administrative reform process in Vietnam. Currently, the model of local government organization including: People's Council and People's Committee in urban areas still has many different opinions Le (Le Cam Ha, 2020).

Nguyen Thi Thuy on "Orientation for building urban government in Vietnam today" in the Journal of Political Science, No. 8/2020, the article focuses on analyzing the content of the concept of urban government, understanding the practical implementation of building urban government in Vietnam today; at the same time, proposing orientations to better implement the building of urban government in Vietnam in the future (Nguyen Thi Thuy, 2020).

The article "*Hanoi builds a streamlined, effective and efficient urban government model*" by author Viet Anh published in the Communist Magazine, November 26, 2018, affirmed: In the process of operating and managing according to the urban government model, the renewal and strengthening of the relationship between the Party committee, the Fatherland Front, political and social organizations and the levels of

government in Hanoi city is a content that is given special attention in order to maintain the leadership role of the Party, promote the people's right to self-governance; improve the effectiveness and efficiency of urban government, meet the requirements and tasks in the context of urbanization and the process of international integration that is taking place strongly (Viet Anh, 2018).

In the article *"Ho Chi Minh City: Urban government is being implemented urgently, streamlined, ensuring effectiveness and efficiency of operation"* by author Long Ho on the Ho Chi Minh City Party Committee's Electronic News Page. From the practical experience of building local government in Ho Chi Minh City in the past, the author proposed orientations and methods for developing urban government towards streamlining, ensuring effectiveness and efficiency of operation such as: Strengthening autonomy and self-responsibility in urban government management; Continuing to promote decentralization and delegation of authority to urban government (Long Ho, 2018).

Author An Tran with the article *"Streamlined and efficient urban government"* in Nhan Dan newspaper stated that: In piloting the urban government model, Hanoi city has implemented the "reduction" of the ward-level people's council organization in districts and Son Tay town. Although this may create pressure on other departments in the local government, the reality shows that this streamlining has brought many positive effects in management, especially in resolving administrative procedures to serve people and businesses (An Tran, 2020).

Studies on urban governance in Vietnam consistently emphasize the need to innovate the organizational and operational models of urban governments towards a streamlined, effective, and efficient model that meets the requirements of socio-economic development in the new context. These studies have proposed numerous specific solutions, ranging from administrative reform and streamlining the apparatus to improving the quality of the workforce, and applying information technology and building e-government.

A Streamlined, Effective, and Efficient Municipal Government

The Vietnamese dictionary explains that "tinh" means "1. having the ability to recognize even very small, complex, and subtle things. 2. Achieving a high level of proficiency, mastering and becoming proficient." "Gòn" means "having balance, giving the feeling that nothing is superfluous" (Hoang Phe (editor), 2000). Similarly, "hieu luc" means "actual effect as required," according to which an effective government organization is one that implements the law correctly, promptly, and with results appropriate to its assigned functions and tasks.

Efficiency is "the actual result of work" (Center for Lexicography, 2008, p. 548) by which an efficient government organization can be understood as a government that achieves management results commensurate with the level of resource expenditure, both economic and social.

According to authors Ho Tan Sang and Mai Thi Hong Lien, "An effective and efficient State and Government is one that is capable of creating development; a State and Government that truly serves the people, serves the national and ethnic interests... This process must adhere to the principle set forth by VI Lenin: "Better to have fewer but better," along with an open and dynamic society of all strata of the people" (Ho Tan Sang and Mai Thi Hong Lien, 2018, p.9). According to this concept, we can understand that streamlined, effective, and efficient means having fewer but better, operating with a developmental nature, prioritizing serving the people, national and ethnic interests. Building urban governments towards streamlined, effective, and efficient governance is a process of strongly reforming the organizational structure, operating mechanisms, and management methods of governments in urban areas to meet the requirements of rapid and sustainable urban development in the new period; Simultaneously, it aims to improve the quality and efficiency of public service delivery, enhance transparency, accountability, and the satisfaction of citizens and businesses. Current urban development and municipal governance practices demonstrate the need for a municipal government that meets the following general requirements:

Firstly, the administrative apparatus can be streamlined by reducing the number of government levels, and specialized agencies can be organized in a way that manages multiple sectors and fields.

Secondly, maximize the application of information technology and implement digital transformation in

government operations to facilitate services for citizens and businesses.

Thirdly, by putting citizens at the center, functional departments can connect with each other to share information and coordinate transactions more effectively with citizens and businesses, providing the services that citizens need, in the way citizens want, at the time citizens deem appropriate.

However, to achieve the above requirements, more specific requirements and criteria are needed: Streamlining the government apparatus is an important goal in state administrative reform, aiming to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of management, including the following elements: Reducing administrative layers; optimizing personnel; reforming administrative procedures... A streamlined urban government apparatus is a state management system in urban areas organized with a simple, flexible structure that easily adapts to changes in the environment. This apparatus has an optimized number of agencies, units, and officials to minimize duplication of functions and tasks, and ensure high work efficiency. A streamlined urban government ensures simplified administrative processes and procedures, efficient use of human resources through training and improved recruitment mechanisms, and the application of information technology and improved work processes to quickly and effectively meet the needs of citizens and businesses. The effectiveness of municipal government refers to its ability and strength in using power and legal tools, policies, and decisions to govern and control those under its control. This aims to achieve management objectives, satisfy practical social needs, and deliver tangible results. The effectiveness of municipal government is demonstrated through the efficiency of administrative decisions, the ability to respond clearly and decisively to issues, compliance with superior orders, and smooth coordination among agencies. It also encompasses the government's capacity to perform its assigned functions and tasks, achieve its stated goals, and meet the needs of its citizens.

Therefore, building a streamlined, effective, and efficient urban government must first and foremost be based on the Party's guidelines and policies, and the State's laws and regulations. The legal environment plays a decisive role in building a streamlined, effective, and efficient urban government because in a rule-of-law state, all organizations and individuals must abide by the law; the law is supreme, and no organization or individual is above the law. Therefore, correctly understanding the role of a streamlined, effective, and efficient urban government in the current development context, and promptly improving the legal environment, will promote the development of cities into socio-economic centers of the provinces, providing a basis for urban governments at all levels to operate effectively and efficiently, shifting from paper-based work to electronic management and processing. Improve the rate of receiving and processing administrative procedures and public services at levels 3 and 4, aiming to better serve citizens and businesses.

The establishment of urban governance suitable to the development requirements and management practices of cities nationwide was raised relatively early; however, the 1992 Constitution, amended and supplemented in 2001, did not include any amendments or additions to Chapter IX concerning the organization and operation of People's Councils and People's Committees. The Law on the Organization of People's Councils and People's Committees of 2003, essentially maintained the organizational and operational model, only adding some tasks and powers related to urban management for People's Councils and People's Committees of centrally-governed cities, districts, towns, provincial cities, and wards.

Since the Doi Moi (Renovation) period (1986), Vietnam's urbanization process has undergone significant transformations. Between 2000 and 2010, Vietnam accelerated its urbanization rate, ranking among the fastest-growing countries in the region (an annual increase of 2.8%). Urban population growth reached over 3% per year. From 2011 to 2020, the urbanization rate continued to increase rapidly alongside economic development, promoting the shift in economic and labor structure towards industrialization and modernization. Urbanization has created urban areas with expanded economic space and a favorable investment and business environment, developed infrastructure, abundant labor resources, and a large market. This has facilitated the development of industries and services, attracted FDI, and promoted the shift in economic structure towards industrialization, improving productivity and the quality of economic growth. The two major metropolitan areas (Hanoi Capital Region and Ho Chi Minh City Region) are increasingly playing the role of leading economic growth poles. Medium and small cities are receiving

investment and development based on fully exploiting the advantages and potential of all regions, linking and supporting each other, including rural areas, so that all regions develop; urban economic growth averages 12-15% per year, 1.2 to 1.5 times the growth of the national economy. In 2020, it is estimated that the urban economy contributed about 70% of the country's GDP. Of these, the five centrally-governed cities, although accounting for only 2.9% of the area and about 22% of the population, contributed 46.8% of the national GDP, attracted 30% of the total cumulative FDI capital, and 32.8% of the total import and export turnover of the country. Labor productivity in major cities in Vietnam is higher than the national average. Urban government revenue has increased significantly, contributing substantially to urban development investment and the national budget. The number of localities that are financially self-sufficient and contribute to the central budget is steadily increasing: 11 localities in the 2007-2010 period, 13 in the 2011-2015 period, and 16 in the 2016-2020 period.

Vietnam is one of the countries with the fastest urbanization rate in East Asia. As of the end of 2023, the country had 902 urban areas, including 2 special-class cities (Hanoi and Ho Chi Minh City), 22 Class I cities, 36 Class II cities, 45 Class III cities, 95 Class IV cities, and 702 Class V cities. The urbanization rate is projected to reach over 50% by 2030 and 70% by 2050; the total number of urban areas nationwide is expected to be around 1,000-1,200; several national and regional urban centers will be formed, achieving indicators in healthcare, education and training, and urban culture equivalent to the average level of cities in the top 4 ASEAN countries; and the urban economy will contribute approximately 85% to the national GDP. To build a network of national and regional smart city centers with international connectivity, and to have 3-5 cities with regionally and internationally recognized brands by 2030.

Urbanization in Vietnam has achieved tremendous results, but it also reveals many serious problems. These include uneven urbanization across regions and a low urbanization rate compared to the world average. Development is primarily extensive with low density, leading to wasted land. Many inner-city areas remain underutilized, with 50-60% of urban land still used for agriculture. The urbanization process has not been well integrated with industrialization and modernization, resulting in an unbalanced and disconnected urban distribution. Renovation and upgrading in major cities like Hanoi and Ho Chi Minh City are very limited, reaching only about 1% of the total number of old apartment buildings. New urban development does not meet sustainability criteria, lacks appropriate research for each region, and does not prioritize distinctive culture and architecture. The sudden population increase is overloading transportation, water supply, waste management, electricity, healthcare, and education systems. Traffic congestion, environmental pollution, and a lack of affordable housing are common problems in major cities like Hanoi and Ho Chi Minh City. Urbanization is concentrated in large cities, creating a disparity in development between urban and rural areas, leading to a widening gap between rich and poor. Urban infrastructure struggles to adapt to climate change and is frequently overloaded, coupled with increasing environmental pollution.

Some Solutions for Building a Streamlined, Efficient, and Effective Urban Government Today

Strong Determination is Needed in Transforming the Urban Government Organizational Model towards a Streamlined, Effective, and Efficient System

To transform urban areas into centers of economic, political, cultural, and social development for the province, it is necessary to build a model of urban governance that suits local characteristics. This requires a streamlined, effective, and efficient government system, with strong determination from the Provincial Party Committee, the Provincial People's Council, and the Provincial People's Committee. The understanding of urban governance remains vague among civil servants, resulting in a lack of commitment from everyone. While the application of information technology to government operations is necessary, the professional skills of this workforce are still limited. Therefore, to successfully build an effective urban government, strong political determination is needed. This determination includes: Strengthening leadership and guidance from all levels; Promoting capacity building for civil servants; and Developing a

clearer legal framework and model for urban governance. To implement these objectives, the following solutions are necessary:

- The Provincial Party Committee needs to quickly unify the Party's viewpoints and policies within the Standing Committee to develop a Resolution on building a streamlined, effective, and efficient urban government as a basis for leadership and implementation. The Resolution must clearly state the viewpoints, objectives, content, and measures for building a streamlined, effective, and efficient urban government .
- Developing a plan to streamline the organizational structure of the provincial political system in general and urban governments in particular, towards greater efficiency and effectiveness, lays an important foundation for Party committees and local governments to quickly begin implementation. This plan, aimed at streamlining the organizational structure of the provincial political system and urban governments, is considered a " reform " to strengthen the Party's leadership role over the political system and urban governments; improve the effectiveness and efficiency of state management; and build a team of capable and responsible officials and civil servants.
- The Provincial People's Council, with its functions and duties, needs to unanimously issue resolutions and policies on building urban governments in a streamlined, effective, and efficient manner, creating a solid legal basis for all levels and sectors to effectively implement them. The Provincial People's Council needs to have a specific plan to seriously and decisively implement the resolutions, projects, and policies of the Provincial Party Committee and the Provincial People's Council in building urban governments in a streamlined, effective, and efficient manner. Strengthen inspection and supervision of implementation, and periodically organize reviews and summaries to adjust the model to suit the practical conditions of urban areas.

Therefore, to build a streamlined, effective, and efficient urban government at the provincial level, it requires correct understanding and strong determination from the Provincial Party Committee, People's Council, and People's Committee at all levels. A decisive policy and plan for implementation are necessary to build a streamlined, effective, and efficient urban government at the provincial level, thereby accelerating socio-economic development in urban areas.

Early Identification of Models and Unified Application of Government Organizational Models for Each Type of Urban Area

It is necessary to find a suitable organizational model and operating mechanism for local government in urban areas. The differences between urban and rural management needs, along with the diverse economic, social, and cultural development in urban environments, create an urgent need for a change in the current government model. The traditional three-tiered model (province, district, commune) is no longer effective in this context, as development and social relationships are becoming increasingly complex. Therefore, urban governments need a streamlined organizational model that still ensures centralized and unified management to effectively oversee economic, cultural, and social activities. To meet this requirement, it is necessary to research and develop a specific urban government model and promote the drafting of a law on the organization of urban governments to create an appropriate legal basis for the operation of government in cities and towns. The focus should be on perfecting the institutional framework for urban governments. To achieve this, further research and evaluation of the current urban governance model are needed to create a streamlined, effective, and efficient system that aligns with the principles of a socialist rule of law state. One solution is to amend the Law on the Organization of Local Governments to unify the organizational model between urban and rural governments nationwide.

Furthermore, innovation in local government operations, coupled with organizational reform, is a key element in the local administrative reform process. The government has issued decrees such as Decree No. 24/2014/ND-CP and its amendments to reduce the number of agencies under the Provincial People's Council, thereby clearly defining their functions and tasks. This reform aims to enhance the management and service capacity of provincial and district-level governments in specialized management areas. In addition, the reform of the organizational structure of specialized agencies under the People's Councils and People's Committees of urban areas will also be carried out according to the following basic proposed directions:

streamlined, effective, and efficient urban governance model to all urban areas within a province. A scientific basis for urban governance organization needs to be developed and perfected, distinguishing between urban and rural governance. The current legal framework regarding the organization and operation of urban governance within the province should be improved, creating a legal environment that ensures effective operation and a streamlined, dynamic organizational structure. In the short term, relevant state agencies should review, supplement, and comprehensively refine legal documents regulating the functions, tasks, powers, and organizational structure of each administrative level according to the urban governance model, ensuring legality, rationality, consistency, and interconnectedness to minimize overlaps or outdated regulations.

Secondly, strengthen decentralization for agencies within urban governments.

The institutional framework for decentralizing state management at the local level needs to be perfected, emphasizing the necessity of reform between urban government levels from province to ward. This process includes strengthening decentralization and delegation of authority to enhance the autonomy and accountability of the government, thereby improving the efficiency of urban management. Further amendments to the Law on the Organization of Local Government and a review of existing legal documents are necessary to implement clearer decentralization for issues specific to urban areas, such as land management and infrastructure development. In particular, a mechanism for budget decentralization for urban governments also needs to be studied.

Thirdly, reform the organizational structure and functions and tasks of the People's Committees of cities/towns and wards.

It is necessary to clearly define the functions and responsibilities of the City People's Committee and the Ward People's Committees in urban government models, and to improve the organizational model of specialized agencies under the City People's Committee. This should clearly define the functions and responsibilities of specialized agencies assisting the City People's Committee in managing urban sectors and fields such as land, infrastructure construction, and urban development control. The tasks of departments, agencies, and equivalent bodies should be adjusted to overcome overlapping functions and responsibilities, with the city government strengthening sectoral management; the City People's Committee and Ward People's Committees should only perform tasks as delegated or authorized by higher-level authorities.

Continue to Improve the Institutional Framework for Decentralization and Delegation of Power between Local Governments and the Governments of Subordinate Cities

The decentralization of state management between provincial governments and cities within provinces is a crucial issue in the context of building a socialist rule of law state in Vietnam today. Through decentralization, the role of each level of government is clearly defined, helping to effectively address national issues and local tasks. Decentralization requires coordination among different levels, departments, and sectors to avoid overlap and to harness the dynamism and creativity of local governments. In particular, urban governments need a high degree of autonomy to leverage advantages and attract external resources for socio-economic development. Clear regulations on the authority and responsibilities of each level of government are necessary in legal documents to ensure effective state governance. Current urban management practices face many challenges such as population management, environmental protection, and citizens' rights; therefore, a high degree of autonomy from urban governments is essential to quickly resolve these issues.

To enhance decentralization and delegation of power to municipal governments, appropriate and coordinated measures are necessary. Specifically, these include:

Firstly, clearly define the position and nature of municipal governments in relation to higher-level authorities. Municipal governments have the right to autonomy and self-responsibility in deciding and implementing policies and laws that are delegated to them. The principle of rational delegation of authority must be upheld: the level with the best capacity to perform its duties should be given full authority, along with the necessary conditions. Higher-level agencies must strengthen inspection and supervision without interfering too deeply in the work of lower levels.

Secondly, decentralization and delegation of power between the central government and municipal

governments is one of the important aspects to ensure the effectiveness of state management, especially in the context of rapid urbanization. Rational decentralization and delegation of power will help enhance the autonomy, accountability, and capacity of each level of government, while promoting sustainable socio-economic development. Therefore, proposals for decentralization and delegation of power between local governments and the governments of subordinate municipalities (cities, towns) should be specifically as follows: Decentralization based on the principle of autonomy and accountability ; delegation of authority to issue certain legal documents ; delegation of authority for organization and personnel at the provincial level ; delegation in planning and infrastructure development management ; delegation in budget and public finance management ; delegation in population management and social security ...

Ensuring the Necessary Conditions for a Streamlined, Effective, and Efficient Urban Governance Model

To build a streamlined, effective, and efficient urban government, supporting conditions play an indispensable role. Two of the most important conditions are building a team of officials and civil servants, and developing e-government and digital government to meet the requirements and tasks of digital transformation. Specifically, building each supporting element requires the following: *Ensuring financial resources at the provincial level urban government.*

To attract financial resources for local socio-economic development, especially in urban areas, many countries have adopted specific financial mechanisms and policies. These mechanisms mainly focus on budget decentralization, tax incentives, credit policies, and land finance management. As a result, localities can mobilize resources to achieve socio-economic development goals, contributing to national economic growth. In the context of developing provincial-level urban governance, the development of specific mechanisms to optimize financial resources has not received adequate attention. To enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of urban governance, it is necessary to establish fiscal autonomy mechanisms for local governments through the self-collection of certain taxes. Some proposed solutions include:

- Increase the role of property tax: Develop property tax as a sustainable source of revenue to support infrastructure investment.
- Enhancing autonomy in service fee decisions: The right to determine the fee levels associated with the services provided will help localities increase their financial autonomy.
- Change the way revenue is divided between the central and local governments: Apply a fair distribution based on the population and economic development level of each region.
- Clarity regarding budget expenditure responsibilities: Avoid overlapping in budget allocation and improve coordination among governments.
- Regulations on expenditure and spending limits: Research allows municipal authorities to determine expenditures appropriate to local conditions and allocate budgets to priority areas such as education, science and technology, and the environment.

Conclusion

Building a streamlined, effective, and efficient urban government is an essential requirement in the context of the rapid development of modern cities. Streamlining the administrative apparatus, clearly defining functions and responsibilities, strongly applying digital transformation, and improving the quality of the workforce will help urban governments operate more professionally and better serve citizens and businesses. A flexible, transparent urban governance model capable of responding quickly to socio-economic changes will create a solid foundation for sustainable development. Therefore, reforming the organization and operation of urban governments is not only an urgent solution but also a long-term strategic direction to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of state management and enhance the quality of life for citizens.

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